

Ion Exchange Kinetics of Alkaline Earth Metals on Zirconium(IV) Phosphoantimonate Cation Exchanger : Energy and Entropy of Activation as a Linear Function of Ionic Mobilities and Radii

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The Nernst-Planck equations have been applied to study the ion exchange kinetics on the surface of zirconium(IV) phosphoantimonate for $Mg^{2+}-H^+$, $Ca^{2+}-H^+$, $Sr^{2+}-H^+$ and $Ba^{2+}-H^+$ exchanges under conditions favouring a particle diffusion phenomenon. Various kinetic parameters, such as self-diffusion coefficient (D_o), energy of activation (E_a) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) have been evaluated. The energy and entropy of activation vary linearly with the ionic radii and mobilities.

Inorganic ion exchangers are well known materials for the separation of metal ions^{1,2}. They are superior to the organic resins as they are resistant to heat and radiation. For the industrial employment of inorganic ion exchangers the rate of reaction in the ion exchange process is of great importance. Kinetic studies have been performed mostly on zirconium phosphate³, zirconium oxide⁴, stannic oxide⁵ and on antimonate of zirconium, iron and tin⁶. Moreover, these studies are based on old βt criterion⁷ which is not very useful for a true ion exchange process because of different effective diffusion coefficients; in such a case the Nernst-Planck⁸ equations should be more appropriate. The zirconium- and antimony-based ion exchangers have received great attention because of their excellent ion exchange behaviour and chemical applications^{2,9} and the kinetic studies are rarely made on double salts¹⁰⁻¹². Zirconium(IV) phosphoantimonate has been successfully utilised in thin layer¹³, paper¹⁴, column¹⁵ and electrochromatography¹⁶. The present work summarises the study on zirconium(IV) phosphoantimonate as cation exchanger, taking alkaline earth metal ions as exchanging species with H^+ ions.

Results and Discussion

A study of the concentration effect on the rate of the exchanger for $Mg^{2+}-H^+$ exchange at 33° shows that the initial rate of exchange is proportional to $[Mg^{2+}]$ upto 0.05 M and becomes constant at and above this

concentration. Under the conditions of particle diffusion control, a relatively large particle size of the exchanger and vigorous shaking, the fractional attainment of equilibrium is given by equation (1),

$$U(\tau) = \frac{\text{Amount of exchange in time } t}{\text{Amount of exchange in infinite time (at equilibrium)}} \quad (1)$$

A plot of $U(\tau)$ vs t (Fig. 1) indicates that the fractional attainment of equilibrium is faster at higher temperature. The present system may be considered to follow the infinite solution volume condition¹⁷ because

Fig. 1. Plot of $U(\tau)$ vs t for $Mg^{2+}-H^+$ exchanges at different temperatures on zirconium(IV) phosphoantimonate : (●) 65°, (○) 50°, (▲) 33° and (Δ) 25°.

$CV \gg \bar{C}\bar{V}$, where C and \bar{C} are the metal ion concentrations in the solution and the exchange phase respectively, and V and \bar{V} are the volumes of these phases. The Nernst-Planck equations can be solved with some additional assumptions¹⁷ which are valid for an inorganic ion exchanger as the swelling changes and the specific interactions are not significant in this case. As a result, we obtain a coupled interdiffusion coefficient \bar{D}_{AB} , the value of which depends on the relative concentrations of the counter ions A and B in the exchanger phase (\bar{C}_A and \bar{C}_B). For $\bar{C}_A \ll \bar{C}_B$, the inter-diffusion coefficient assumes the value \bar{D}_A , A being counter ion initially present in the ion exchanger phase. Since in the present study the exchanger is taken in the H^+ form, \bar{D}_A may be replaced by \bar{D}_H . The numerical results can be expressed¹⁷ by the explicit approximations,

$$U(\tau) = 1 - \exp [\pi^2(F_1(\alpha) \tau + F_2(\alpha) \tau^2 + F_3(\alpha) \tau^3)] - 2 \quad (2)$$

where, $\tau = \bar{D}_H t / r_0^2$, the mobility ratio $(\alpha) = \bar{D}_H / \bar{D}_M$, r_0 is the particle radius and \bar{D}_M the interdiffusion coefficient of the metal ion. Under the condition $1 \leq \alpha \leq 20$ and the charge ratio $Z_H / Z_M = 1/2$ which were fulfilled in the present case, the three functions $F_1(\alpha)$, $F_2(\alpha)$ and $F_3(\alpha)$ can be expressed¹⁷ as

$$F_1(\alpha) = - \frac{1}{0.64 + 0.36\alpha^{0.668}} \quad (a)$$

$$F_2(\alpha) = - \frac{1}{0.96 + 2.0\alpha^{0.4635}} \quad (b)$$

$$F_3(\alpha) = - \frac{1}{0.27 + 0.09\alpha^{1.14}} \quad (c)$$

A solution of equation (2) for each value of $U(\tau)$ gives a corresponding value of τ , by graphical method. Table 1 summarises the various τ values for alkaline earth metals at four different temperatures while the slope values of the τ vs t plots are given in Table 2. The particle size has a marked effect on the rate of exchange. A plot of S vs $1/r_0^2$ (Fig. 2) shows that the rate of exchange is inversely proportional to the particle size, a fundamental condition for a particle diffusion phenomenon.

The S values are related with \bar{D}_H as

$$S = \bar{D}_H / r_0^2$$

TABLE 1 - τ VALUES FOR ALKALINE EARTHS - H^+ EXCHANGES ON ZIRCONIUM(IV) PHOSPHOANTIMONATE CATION EXCHANGER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND TIME INTERVALS

Time min	25°	33°	50°	65°
Mg²⁺-H⁺ :				
1.0	0.080	0.095	0.115	0.130
1.5	0.120	0.145	0.165	0.190
2.0	0.170	0.200	0.225	0.235
2.5	0.220	0.250	0.290	0.320
3.0	0.270	0.290	0.325	0.380
Ca²⁺-H⁺ :				
1.0	0.070	0.080	0.110	0.135
1.5	0.110	0.125	0.155	0.180
2.0	0.145	0.165	0.200	0.255
2.5	0.180	0.225	0.270	0.300
3.0	0.220	0.255	0.325	0.355
Sr²⁺-H⁺ :				
1.0	0.090	0.110	0.125	0.150
1.5	0.135	0.165	0.195	0.260
2.0	0.170	0.230	0.260	0.300
2.5	0.225	0.270	0.345	0.380
3.0	0.270	0.320	0.380	0.445
Ba²⁺-H⁺ :				
1.0	0.090	0.110	0.155	0.170
1.5	0.135	0.165	0.200	0.255
2.0	0.190	0.220	0.270	0.370
2.5	0.245	0.290	0.360	0.435
3.0	0.280	0.325	0.410	0.500

TABLE 2 - SLOPE VALUES OF VARIOUS τ VS TIME PLOTS FOR ALKALINE EARTHS- H^+ EXCHANGES ON ZIRCONIUM(IV) PHOSPHOANTIMONATE

Metal ion	Particle radius	$5 \times 10^3 (s^{-1})$ value at			
		25°	33°	50°	65°
Mg ²⁺	125	1.42	1.67	1.83	2.13
Ca ²⁺	125	1.22	1.41	1.81	1.97
Sr ²⁺	125	1.50	1.78	2.11	2.47
Ba ²⁺	125	1.55	1.80	2.28	2.90

The values of $-\log \bar{D}_H$ obtained using this equation were plotted against $1/T$. Straight lines are obtained for all the metal ions studied (Fig. 3), justifying the validity of the Arrhenius equation,

$$D_H = D_0 \exp(-E_a/RT) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2 Plot of S vs $1/r_0^2$ for Mg^{2+} at 33° on zirconium(IV) phosphoantimonate cation exchanger.

Fig. 3. $\log \bar{D}_H$ vs $1/T$ plots for the alkaline earth II^+ -exchangers on zirconium(IV) phosphoantimonate : (O) Mg^{II} , (●) Ca^{II} , (Δ) Sr^{II} and (\blacktriangle) Ba^{II} .

The pre-exponential constants (D_0) were obtained from intercept of these lines and the values of activation energy (E_a) calculated from equation (3).

The entropies of activation (ΔS^*) were obtained by substituting the D_0 values in the equation,

$$D_0 = 2.72 d^2 \frac{kT}{h} \exp \left(\frac{\Delta S^*}{R} \right)$$

where, k and h are Boltzmann and Planck constants, d is the ionic jump distance¹⁸ taken as 5 Å, R the gas

constant and T is 273 K. The values of the diffusion coefficient (D_0), energy of activation (E_a) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*), thus obtained are summarised in Table 3. An increase in the values of E_a and ΔS^* with

TABLE 3 – SELF-DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT, ENERGY OF ACTIVATION AND ENTROPY OF ACTIVATION OF ALKALINE EARTHS- H^+ EXCHANGES ON ZIRCONIUM(IV) PHOSPHOANTIMONATE

Migrating ion	Ionic mobility $\times 10^{-9}$ $m^2V^{-1}s^{-1}$	Ionic radius ^a nm	Hydrated ionic radius nm	$D_0 \times 10^{-10}$ m^2s^{-1}	E_a $kJ mol^{-1}$	ΔS^* $J K^{-1} mol^{-1}$
Mg^{2+}	55	7.8	31	6.760	8.362 0	-91.08
Ca^{2+}	62	10.6	20	9.015	9.459 5	-69.53
Sr^{2+}	62	12.7	18	17.579	10.767 6	-63.98
Ba^{2+}	66	14.3	15	48.978	13.431 3	-55.46

^aGoldschmidt's value.

Average radius of the exchanger particles used 125 nm.

the ionic radii and mobilities¹⁰ of alkaline earth metals is a general behaviour of the inorganic ion exchangers. Fig. 4 shows a linear variation of E_a and ΔS^* with ionic radii, hydrated ionic radii and ionic mobilities.

Fig. 4. Variation of E_a and ΔS^* with ionic radii, hydrated ionic radii and ionic mobilities of alkaline earth metals on zirconium(IV) phosphoantimonate.

Zirconium(IV) arsenophosphate and arsenosilicates also show such behaviour¹⁰. The ion exchange capacity of this material for different metal ions follows the following order $Ba^{2+} > Sr^{2+} > Ca^{2+} > Mg^{2+}$. The same order of the mobilities and activation energies is also obtained in the present study.

A comparison of the kinetic behaviour of various inorganic ion exchangers based on zirconium and antimony (Fig. 5) indicates that the diffusion rate, activation energy and entropy of activation are in general lower on antimony-based salts. A positive entropy change for zirconium(IV) arsenosilicate probably accounts for the high efficiency of its columns¹⁰. Thus, the studies based on Nernst-Planck equations, give a more appropriate explanation for the separation mechanism on inorganic ion exchangers as compared to the old βI criterion because of the introduction of the term 'mobility' in the new approach.

Experimental

Zirconyl chloride (Romali, India), antimony pentachloride (Fluka) and trisodium orthophosphate (E. Merck) were used. All other reagents and chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

A water-bath incubator shaker, maintaining a constant temperature ($\pm 0.5^\circ$) was used for the equilibrium studies.

Zirconium(IV) phosphoantimonate was prepared as follows¹⁴. An aqueous 0.1 M trisodium orthophosphate solution, an aqueous 0.1 M zirconyl chloride solution and an 0.05 M antimony pentachloride solution (in 4 M HCl) were admixed in 1 : 1 : 1 volume ratio and pH of the gel was adjusted to 1.0 by adding aqueous ammonia. After keeping for 24 h at room temperature, the slurry was filtered, washed with demineralised water and dried at 45° before putting in water to form small granules. The granules were then placed in 1M HNO_3 to convert them into H^+ -form and were finally washed and dried at 45° before use. The ion exchange capacities of the exchanger for Na, Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba metals were 1.86, 1.31, 2.03, 2.04 and 2.10 respectively.

Kinetic measurements : Zirconium phosphoantimonate (ZPA) was well-ground and passed through standard sieves to obtain different mesh sizes (25–50, 780

Fig. 5. Diffusion coefficient, activation energies and entropy of activation for alkaline earth metals exchanging with H^+ on different zirconium and antimony based inorganic ion exchangers : (O) antimonite acid, (●) antimony silicate, (Δ) zirconium(IV) arsenophosphate, (▲) zirconium(IV) phosphosilicate, (*) zirconium(IV) phosphoantimonate and (X) zirconium(IV) phosphoantimonate.

50–70, 70–100 and 100–150). Particles of mesh size 50–70 were generally used unless stated otherwise. Fractions (20 ml) of the metal ion solutions (Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba) were shaken with the exchanger in H⁺-form (200 mg) in several stoppered conical flasks at desired temperatures (25, 33, 50 and 65°) for different time intervals¹⁹. The supernatant was removed immediately by filtration and the metal ions were determined in the solution with EDTA titration⁷ using eriochrome black T.

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